

Surgical Management of Giant Intracranial Meningiomas - A Case SeriesAsman Ali¹, Tanmoy Bhuyan²¹Associate Professor, Dept. of Neurosurgery, Cardiothoracic and Neuroscience Center, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital²Senior Resident, Dept. of Neurosurgery, Cardiothoracic and Neuroscience Center, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Tanmoy Bhuyan

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Due to their size and position within the skull, giant intracranial meningiomas present a challenge for neurosurgeons. They are very difficult to be removed due to the challenging tumor dissection and encasement of crucial neurovascular systems. This study aims to present our giant intracranial meningioma series and to compare our experience using advanced surgical technology with the current literature.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective assessment was conducted on the data pertaining to patients diagnosed with massive intracranial meningioma between 2023 and 2024 who underwent surgical management. Patients' radiological, surgical, and demographic details were recorded. A thorough analysis was conducted on the location and size of the tumors as well as the surgical approach.

Results: The study findings indicate that throughout a 1-year period, 30 patients with intracranial meningioma underwent surgical treatment. Of these, 8 (26.7%) had tumors greater than 5 cm in diameter, which were categorized as giant meningiomas. With a mean age of 64.4 years, there were 5 female and 3 male patients. There were 3 tumors near the base of the skull. 5 patients had Simpson grade 1 resection, whereas 3 patients had grade 2 resection. There was no death reported. In conclusion, giant intracranial meningiomas require careful surgical planning. The excision level of these massive tumors is influenced by their location, the neurovascular structures nearby, and the vascular supply. Skull base meningiomas rarely allow for Simpson grade 1 excision.

Keywords: Giant Meningioma, Surgery, Brain.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The most prevalent benign intracranial tumors are meningiomas, which develop from arachnoid cap cells. These extra-axial tumors are relatively slow-growing. [1,2] Cerebral convexity, the parasagittal/falcine area, the sphenoid wing, the tuberculum sellae, and the posterior fossa are the most frequently occurring sites for these tumors. The clinical symptoms of these tumors correlate with the location of the tumors or to raised intra-cranial pressure. Radiological diagnosis is generally made once the tumor reaches a considerable volume as they grow slowly.[1-3]

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT) are the two primary radiological techniques used to diagnose intracranial meningiomas. The origin and borders of the tumor are well defined by MRI.[4] It is also useful in the planning of the surgical approach for tumor excision. Meningiomas can cause erosion or hyperostosis of the bones, which can be revealed on a CT scan. When giant meningiomas calcify or alter the bone, they are also visible on ordinary skull X-rays.[5,6] An-

giography can also be used prior to surgery to identify the tumor's vascular supply and obliterate the feeding channels, which may aid in the tumor's complete excision.[4-6] At the time of diagnosis, meningiomas might be giant (>5 cm) or large (>3 cm).[7,8] The huge size of giant meningiomas, which results in elevated intracranial pressure, and their close proximity to vital anatomical structures makes them different from other types of meningiomas.[8] For this reason, they present as a challenge to neurosurgeons.

The primary treatment for big intracranial meningiomas is surgical excision. To achieve a safe and efficient maximum tumor excision, the surgical strategy for each tumor is tailored based on its size and location.[9,10] The primary objective of surgical treatment is gross complete resection. Due to adhesion and encasement of significant neurovascular structures like the optic nerve, carotid artery, or superior sagittal sinus, it is not usually possible for huge meningiomas.[9-14] This paper intends to highlight our cases of giant cerebral meningioma,

illustrate the surgical challenges associated with these rare tumors, and compare our results with the current literature.

Materials and Methods

We retrospectively reviewed the data of patients diagnosed with meningioma who underwent surgical excision for cerebral tumor between 2023 and 2024. Patients with an intracranial meningioma greater than 5 cm in maximal diameter were included in the study. The demographic, radiographic and surgical characteristics of the patients were examined. Patients' clinical presentation, first neurological assessment and preoperative CT and MRI scans, were all documented. Every patient had a craniotomy planned out prior to surgery, and a neuronavigation system was put in place before the procedure started. For every procedure, the neuronavigation system was employed. The tumor was located and removed using proper surgical techniques.

Only 1 case of a massive skull base meningioma, in which we were unable to achieve Simpson grade 1 resection using classical surgical approach, required the use of endoscopic technique. The extent of resection was described using the Simpson scale.

Results

Meningioma was diagnosed in 30 patients over a period of 1 year. A diagnosis of giant intracranial meningioma was made for 8 (26.7%) of the patients. The mean age of the patients (3 male and 5 female) was 64.4 years (range: 30-83 years). The size and location of tumors are shown in Table 1.

Surgical excision was done for all the patients. In total 9 surgical operations were performed on the 8 patients. 7 patients had their tumors removed in 1 session, and 1 patient had 2 sessions. In 1 patient, the tumor penetrated the subcutaneous layer and destroyed the cranial bony structure. 3 patients had the tumor at the base of their skull, 1 had it on the sphenoid wing, and 1 in the temporal fossa. Of them, 3 patients underwent Simpson grade 2 resection, whereas the 5 patients without skull base location had grade 1 resection. Only 1 patient had preoperative feeding artery embolization, and in that patient, surgical resection was accomplished successfully and without significant bleeding.

No patient experienced a decline in neurological function or died as a result of surgery. 2 patients had cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) accumulation at the surgical site and received conservative treatment.

Table 1: Demographic, Radiological, Surgical, and Histological Characteristics of Patients who Underwent Surgery for Giant Intracranial Meningioma

Patient no.	Age (years)/sex	Location	Size (cm)	Origin	Resection grade (Simpson grade)	Histological diagnosis
1	30/Male	Left frontal	7 × 5.2 × 6	Falx cerebri	Grade 1	Meningioma WHO grade I
2	49/Male	Olfactory groove (skull base)	5.7 × 4.2 × 5	Anterior skull base dura	Grade 2	Meningioma WHO grade I
3	82/Male	Right posterior parietal	4.6 × 6 × 5.3	Convexity dura	Grade 1	Meningioma WHO grade II
4	78/Female	Anterior clinoid (skull base)	5 × 6 × 6	Skull base dura	Grade 2	Meningioma WHO grade I
5	83/Female	Sphenoid Wing (skull base)	6.7 × 5.5 × 6.3	Skull base dura	Grade 1	Meningioma WHO grade I
6	53/Female	Left frontoparietal	6.4 × 7.8 × 5.6	Falx cerebri	Grade 1	Meningioma WHO grade I
7	70/Female	Left posterior parietal	7 × 5 × 7	Convexity dura	Grade 1	Meningioma WHO grade I
8	70/Female	Left temporal fossa	7.3 × 7.1 × 5.1	Sphenoid wing dura	Grade 2	Meningioma WHO grade I

Figure 1: Intraoperative finding of a patient of giant intracranial meningioma patient

Figure 2: Preoperative MRI finding of a patient with giant intracranial meningioma

Discussion

The clinical results of 8 patients who had giant intracranial meningiomas surgically treated were presented in the study. The relevant surgical anatomy and surgical procedures were highlighted and emphasis was laid on the surgical problems of these rare tumors. Extra-axial meningiomas are tumors that typically appear alone, but they can also be associated with other tumors like schwannomas or

gliomas.[15,16] Children are rarely diagnosed with these tumors, however adults are affected more.[17]

Solitary fibrous tumors, schwannomas (in the posterior fossa), gliomas, hemangiopericytomas, dural metastases, chordomas and pituitary macroadenomas are among the differential diagnoses for meningiomas.[18] There is no exact definition of giant meningioma in the literature, some authors have

defined giant meningioma as a tumor >4.5 cm; others included a maximum diameter of 5 cm, 6 cm, or 7 cm.[7–13] While these tumors have been referred to as huge meningiomas[12] by some writers, most publications classify tumors larger than 5 cm as giant meningiomas. Therefore, in the present study the lower limit for considering a meningioma to be giant was 5 cm.

The majority of meningiomas are slow-growing tumors, with a growth rate of approximately 2.4 mm annually.[14,19] They rarely exhibit clinical symptoms until the tumor reaches a significant size due to their slow growth.

Giant meningiomas are exceedingly uncommon and pose a challenge for a complete excision. Because of their compressive effects on brain tissue, elevated intracranial pressure, and hemodynamic alteration secondary to vascular compression, these tumors are classified as complex lesions. In almost half of the cases with meningioma, there is varying degrees of vasogenic edema in the surrounding brain tissue.[20] Peritumoral edema and tumor water content may be decreased with preoperative corticosteroid therapy.[21] Three key concerns with surgery for giant meningiomas are as follows: 1) Difficulty in achieving adequate tumor exposure due to bridging veins and surrounding arteries; 2) Prolonged surgical times due to increased blood loss; and 3) Difficulty in releasing encased or involved main cerebral arteries and cranial nerves.[22-23]

Therefore, detailed preoperative information including the location of critical arteries and nerves is essential for a safe surgical excision of giant meningiomas. Coagulation of feeding vessels should be the first step in the surgery of giant intracranial meningioma. Dealing with a tensed brain tissue during approach, dissection, and tumor removal stages is another hurdle surgeons have to face while operating on such tumors which can be alleviated by using microsurgical techniques. The origin of the meningioma should always be targeted first during surgery if possible. Tiny incisions in the dura mater or opening the arachnoid cisterns after craniotomy may allow gradual CSF drainage and a decrease in intracranial pressure. After the dural opening, small cottonoids may be placed around and beneath the meningioma under microscopic guidance, and the brain-tumor interface is protected by these cottonoids until the release of the tumor tissue from the brain. Gradual separation of adhesions between the brain and the tumor tissue reduces brain traction during tumor resection. A CUSA may be used to debulk the tumor.[19] Following sufficient reduction of tumor volume, the brain tissue pushes the tumor mass more and more toward the surgeon and facilitates the removal of tumor. Involved dura and dural rim is also necessary to achieve Simpson grade 1 resection. For gi-

ant skull base meningiomas, CSF drainage from the basal arachnoid cisterns using trans-sylvian approach allows excellent brain relaxation. Endoscopic techniques for skull base meningiomas provide early tumor devascularization and detachment of tumor from the skull base.[24]

Selection of approach for giant intracranial meningiomas mainly depends on the location of the tumor. Giant convexity meningiomas require a larger craniotomy for safe tumor dissection and removal.[25] The size of craniotomy must be greater than the tumor diameter which should be tailored based on the preoperative CT and MRI scans. Approach to giant skull base meningiomas should be planned based on the location of tumor and tumor size.[7,26,27] Craniofacial approaches are suitable for some skull base meningiomas.[28] Giant anterior fossa or tuberculum sellae meningiomas may be approached using a pterional, subfrontal, or endoscopic endonasal approach. Ventricular meningiomas could be resected by endoscopic techniques using a tubular retractor (port) or via an interhemispheric transcallosal approach under microscopic guidance.[29,30] In the current series, we performed 9 surgical procedures in 8 patients. All patients underwent preoperative CT and MRI scans. Only 1 patient underwent preoperative embolization. 8 procedures were craniotomies with tumor removal using microsurgical techniques and 1 procedure was an extended endoscopic endonasal technique for a skull base meningioma that was subtotally removed with classical microsurgical techniques. Several other series of giant intracranial meningioma were reported previously.[9,12,13] while many others were presented as case reports.[6,22,23,25,26,31,32] Tuna et al.[12] reported 93 patients with giant huge intracranial meningiomas, and they classified meningiomas >6 cm in diameter as giant meningiomas. Mean age was 48.7 years, and mortality was 3.2%. Their study concluded that a larger size of meningioma negatively affects the extent of removal, recurrence rate, postoperative outcome, and mortality.[12] Narayan et al.[9] reported a series of 80 patients with giant intracranial meningioma who were surgically treated over a 20-year period. They considered tumors >5 cm in maximum dimension as giant intracranial meningioma, similar to the current study. The mean age was 56 years in their study, and the mortality rate was 5%. They concluded that a younger age, male sex, use of neuronavigation and a skull base location positively influence recurrence-free survival, whereas Simpson grade 3 or grade 4 excision and poor histological grade negatively influence recurrence-free survival.[9] Özsoy et al.[13] reported in their series of 56 patients with giant meningiomas that the size of tumor and the amount of surgical excision affect the rate of recurrence, mortality, and morbidity. The mean age in their study was 49.75 years, and the mortality was 7.1%.[13] In the

current series we achieved Simpson grade 1 or 2 resection were achieved in all cases, and there were no post-operative mortalities. Attia et al.[33] studied 22 patients with giant anterior clinoidal meningiomas, and they defined these tumors as globular tumors with a maximum diameter of 5 cm or larger, centered around the anterior clinoidal process. They performed a skull base approach with extradural unroofing of the optic canal, extradural clinoidectomy, transdural tumor debulking, early optic nerve decompression, and early identification and control of important neurovascular structures. They achieved Simpson grade 1 or 2 resection in 30.4% of surgeries without mortality.[33] In the current study, only 1 patient presented with a giant meningioma arising from the anterior clinoid process, and that patient underwent Simpson grade 2 tumor resection using microsurgical techniques. Behari et al.[8] studied 4 patients with large/giant meningiomas of the posterior third ventricular region and suggested an occipital transtentorial approach for such tumors.[8] A suboccipital transtentorial approach may be used for meningiomas located in the posterior mediobasal temporal region.[34] If the tumor extends toward the intraorbital region, superior or lateral orbitotomies under navigation guidance are useful techniques to safely remove the tumor.[35] In the current series, none of the patients with giant intraventricular or orbital meningioma.

The surgical management of giant intracranial meningiomas became safer with the use of advanced imaging techniques and intraoperative technologies, such as neuronavigation, 3-D ultrasound, radiofrequency thermocoagulation, intraoperative angiography, and electrophysiological monitoring.[9,27,33,35] These developments decreased the morbidity and mortality of these difficult cases. The extent of resection in meningiomas is always measured by Simpson grading in neurosurgery [9], and a gross total resection (Simpson grade 1 and 2) was achieved in all cases. A neuronavigation system enables optimum craniotomy for safe resection by providing the shortest way to reach the tumor. This also increases the resection level of the tumor and survival of the patient.

Tumor bed hematoma, CSF collection or leak, and infection are the major complications of giant intracranial meningiomas surgery.[9,11-13] Insufficient coagulation of tumor bed may cause postoperative hematoma and therefore neurological deficits. Inadequate dural closure may result in CSF collection or leak. In the present study, none of the patients had post-operative hematoma or CSF fistula; however CSF collection occurred in 2 patients and was treated conservatively.

Conclusion

The major limitations of the present study are the

limited study population and the lack of the control group to compare the surgical outcomes and results. Although giant intracranial meningiomas are rare, their surgical management is quite challenging and requires extreme caution for patient safety. Therefore, a good anatomical knowledge and microsurgical skills are required for adequate resection and to overcome the risks of complications.

References

1. Wiemels J, Wrensch M, Claus EB. Epidemiology and etiology of meningioma. *J Neurooncol.* 2010; 99(3):307-314.
2. Buerki RA, Horbinski CM, Kruser T, Horowitz PM, James CD, Lukas RV. An overview of meningiomas. *Future Oncol.* 2018; 14(21): 2161-2177.
3. Wang N, Osswald M. Meningiomas: overview and new directions in therapy. *Semin Neurol.* 2018; 38(1):112-120.
4. Hou W, Ma Y, Xing H, Yin Y. Imaging characteristics and surgical treatment of invasive meningioma. *Oncol Lett.* 2017; 13(5):2965-2970.
5. Huang RY, Bi WL, Griffith B, et al. Imaging and diagnostic advances for intracranial meningiomas. *Neuro Oncol.* 2019;21(Suppl 1):i44-i61.
6. Khairy S, Orz Y. Giant meningioma in skull radiograph. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2017; 2017:bcr2017220833.
7. da Silva CE, de Freitas PEP. Large and giant skull base meningiomas: the role of radical surgical removal. *Surg Neurol Int.* 2015; 6:113.
8. Behari S, Das KK, Kumar A, et al. Large/ giant meningiomas of posterior third ventricular region: falcotentorial or velum interpositum? *Neurol India.* 2014; 62(3):290-295.
9. Narayan V, Bir SC, Mohammed N, Savardekar AR, Patra DP, Nanda A. Surgical management of giant intracranial meningioma: operative nuances, challenges, and outcome. *World Neurosurg.* 2018; 110:e32-e41.
10. Antunes C, Ramos R, Machado MJ, Filipe MA. Giant posterior fossa meningioma: the importance of early diagnosis and challenges concerning treatment. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2019; 12(3):e228454.
11. Samii M, Gerganov VM. Giant meningiomas of the posterior fossa. *J Neurosurg.* 2010; 112(5):905-906.
12. Tuna M, Göçer AI, Gezercan Y, et al. Huge meningiomas: a review of 93 cases. *Skull Base Surg.* 1999; 9(3):227-238.
13. Özsoy KM, Ökten AI, Ateş T, et al. Intracranial benign giant meningiomas: A clinical analysis of 56 cases. *Neurosurg Q.* 2013; 23(1):27-32.
14. Kuratsu JI, Kochi M, Ushio Y. Incidence and

- clinical features of asymptomatic meningiomas. *J Neurosurg*. 2000; 92(5):766-770.
15. Solmaz I, Pusat S, Kural C, Onguru O, Gönül E, Izci Y. Simultaneously occurring oligodendro- glioma and meningioma: rare synchronous primary brain tumors. Case report and literature review. *Neurosurg Q*. 2012; 22(2):133-136.
 16. Izci Y, Secer HI, Gönül E, Ongürü O. Simultaneously occurring vestibular schwannoma and meningioma in the cerebellopontine angle: case report and literature review. *Clin Neuro- pathol*. 2007; 26(5):219-223.
 17. Akay KM, Izci Y, Baysefer A, Atabey C, Kısmet E, Timurkaynak E. Surgical outcomes of cerebellar tumors in children. *Pediatr Neurosurg*. 2004; 40(5):220-225.
 18. Secer HI, Gonul E, Onguru O, Izci Y. Solitary fibrous tumour extending both supratentorially and infratentorially. *J Clin Neurosci*. 2008; 15(7):830-833.
 19. Kurokawa Y, Ishiguro M, Kurokawa TA. Giant true ossified meningioma removed with surgical ultrasonic aspirator with shear wave technology. *Clin Surg*. 2017; 2:1829.
 20. Kim BW, Kim MS, Kim SW, Chang CH, Kim OL. Peritumoral brain edema in meningiomas: correlation of radiologic and pathologic features. *J Korean Neurosurg. Soc*. 2011; 49(1): 26-30.
 21. Kural C, Atac GK, Tehli O, et al. The evaluation of the effects of steroid treatment on the tumor and peritumoral edema by DWI and MR spectroscopy in brain tumors. *Neurol Neurochir Pol*. 2018; 52(4): 495-504.
 22. Kerman M, Dağtekin A, Kaymaz H, Kara NN. Intracranial giant meningioma: a case report. *SDÜ Tıp Fakültesi*. 1998; 5(4):187-190.
 23. Li ZY, Cen Y, Gu M, Wei Y. Giant malignant meningioma invading the calvarial bone and scalp. *J Craniofac Surg*. 2012; 23(2):599-602.
 24. Kutlay M, Durmaz A, Özer İ, et al. Extended endoscopic endonasal approach to the ventral skull base lesions. *Clin Neurol Neurosurg*. 2018; 167:129-140.
 25. Nadkarni T, Desai K, Goel A. Giant meningioma of the cranial vertex - case report. *Neurol Med Chir (Tokyo)*. 2002; 42(3):128-131.
 26. Ion G, Faiyad Z, Poata I, Chiriac A. Combined treatment of a giant anterior skull base meningioma. *Romanian Neurosurgery*. 2018; 32:602-606.
 27. Champagne PO, Lemoine E, Bojanowski MW. Surgical management of giant sphenoid wing meningiomas encasing major cerebral arteries. *Neurosurg Focus*. 2018; 44(4):E12.
 28. Avcı E, Aktüre E, Seçkin H, et al. Level I to III craniofacial approaches based on Barrow classification for treatment of skull base meningiomas: surgical technique, microsurgical anatomy, and case illustrations. *Neurosurg Focus*. 2011; 30(5):E5.
 29. Kutlay M, Kural C, Solmaz I, et al. Fully endoscopic resection of intra-axial brain lesions using neuronavigated pediatric anoscope. *Turk Neurosurg*. 2016; 26(4):491-499.
 30. Secer HI, Duz B, Izci Y, Solmaz I, Tehli O, Gonul E. Tumors of the lateral ventricle: the factors that affected the preference of the surgical approach in 46 patients. *Turk Neurosurg*. 2008; 18(4):345-355.
 31. Jiang YG, Xiang J, Wen F, Zhang LY. Microsurgical excision of the large or giant cerebellopontine angle meningioma. *Minim Invasive Neurosurg*. 2006; 49(1):43-48.
 32. Gutteridge IF, Wallace D. Giant intracranial meningioma without hemianopic visual field loss. *Clin Exp Optom*. 2002; 85(2):101-106.
 33. Attia M, Umansky F, Paldor I, Dotan S, Shoshan Y, Spektor S. Giant anterior clinoidal meningiomas: surgical technique and outcomes. *J Neurosurg*. 2012; 117(4):654-665.
 34. Moftakhar R, Izci Y, Baskaya MK. Microsurgical anatomy of the supracerebellar transtentorial approach to the posterior mediobasal temporal region: technical considerations with a case illustration. *Neurosurgery*. 2008; 62(3 Suppl 1):1-7.
 35. Hodaj I, Kutlay M, Gonul E, et al. The use of neuronavigation and intraoperative imaging systems in the surgical treatment of orbital tumors. *Turk Neurosurg*. 2014; 24(4):549-557.